

MANAGEMENT PROFILE OF GUIDANCE AND COUNSELING IMPLEMENTATION IN VOCATIONAL SECONDARY SCHOOL

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Abstract

This article is intended to describe the management of the implementation of counseling and guidance in vocational secondary schools. All data are revealed by using the techniques of observation and interview against informants that have data sources that are widely associated with the management of the implementation of counseling and guidance in vocational secondary schools, namely the school counselor and some teachers that help the implementation of counseling and guidance at SMK Negeri I Ponorogo. The results of the descriptive analysis against the management of the implementation of counseling and guidance at SMK Negeri I Ponorogo can be classified in three parts; First, program planning counseling and guidance. Counseling and guidance programs that have been developed at SMK Negeri I Ponorogo have standard and done professionally, because it has been through the planning mechanism, feasibility study, consulting programs and socialization of execution the program. Second, the implementation of a program management counseling and guidance. Implementation of management counseling and guidance at SMK Negeri I Badegan has been done correctly, because it already includes the target learners and stakeholders with system administration and reporting are complete, ranging from program daily, weekly, on a monthly, semiannual and annual, though the supporting facilities and infrastructure facilities is still very minimal. Third, organizational and human resources personnel of counseling and guidance. The conditions of organization and personnel still to be developed, since technically the amount one person concurrently coordinator of counseling and guidance staff assisted with one person taken from teachers of subjects, so haven't been able to provide services maximum, because the comparative number were one teacher with 1200 students.

Keywords: *management counseling and guidance*

A. Introduction

The implementation of school counseling and guidance in Indonesia at this time, has passed a new era with a new paradigm which was more clear and purposeful in accordance with the expectations of the world of education. As Willis (2010:28) that a new paradigm was related to philosophical grounds of counseling and guidance which includes: (1) *paedagogis*, a foundation that was intended to create conditions conducive school for the development of learner with attention to individual differences among learners. (2) *potential*, this meant more counseling and guidance services geared at the development

potential of learners as individuals. As for his weaknesses will gradually by himself. (3) the humanistic-religious, meaning approach to the learners must be humane with the religious way, and the students as human beings was considered able to develop themselves and its potential. (4) professional, i.e. the process of counseling and guidance should be performed in a professional manner on the basis of philosophical, theoretical, knowledgeable and skillful as well as the sharing of counseling and guidance techniques.

The new orientation of the organization of the counseling and guidance services has encouraged a more humanist approach and put forward a positive concept in handling learners. In addition, the National Education goals as spelled out in article 4 of law No. 20 Year 2002 is "the intellectual life of the nation as well as develop human Indonesia intact, the man of faith and pious to God Almighty, ethical sublime, have knowledge and skills, physical and spiritual health, a steady and independent personality and sense of responsibility of civic and nation "(Law No. 20 of RI, 2002). In addition, the refinement of the curriculum the Education Ministry of national education has been carried out with emphasis on competency basis in order to improve the quality of education in Indonesia that can respond to the challenges of change global development of science and technology, and arts and culture. The legislation of the Republic of Indonesia Number 20 years of 2003 (law 20/2003) about the national education system and government regulation of the Republic of Indonesia number 19 Years of 2005 (PP 19/2005) about national education Standards mandated curriculum KTSP (Law No. 20, RI 2003), with reference to the content of the Standard (SI) Standard and competence of graduates (SKL) and based on the guidelines drawn up by the national standards of education (BSNP) (UU RI No. 20, 2003).

Follow up on education policy that mandated law schools, as education providers in the implementation of the curriculum unit level education (KTSP), are required to implement various new paradigm contained therein regarding the basic outline KTSP, principles of curriculum development in KTSP, KTSP components, the goal of the school and standard contents, the competence of graduates, program structure, implementation of the KTSP associated with organizing and learning as well as an evaluation or assessment. Understanding in prespective KTSP, schools, including SMK (Vocational High School) are

expected to develop a curriculum that leads to the development of life skills learners. These include life skills, specific skills and general skills such as personal, social, academic and polytechnic (Director-General of the quality of education, 2008).

In addition, in order to realize the vision of a national education established the year 2025 as a milestone achievement of the people of Indonesia are smart and competitive, Vocational secondary schools as one of the organizers of the education with the concept of vocational graduates are expected to work according the competence and fields of study, has been prepared with typical framework. Is no exception with the Ministry of guidance and konselingnya. It can be seen from the policy are taken from the majority of Vocational secondary schools that give you more for the services portion of counseling and guidance. Particularly associated with hours of tutoring services for special groups/classical. Vocational secondary schools in several areas, many of which provide specific hours for group tutoring service/classical, so that teachers, counselors can provide personal development materials in classes, at least one hour for a week.

One of the things that need to be implemented is management governance. Management according to the Stoner is "The process of planning, organizing, leading and controlling the efforts of organizing members and of using all other organizational resources to achieve stated organizational goals" (Yusuh and Nurihsan, 2004:25). This indicates that management was a process of planning, organizing, directing and controlling all components or parts of the organization by using a variety of sources that exist in order to achieve the purposes for which expected. Therefore, if associated with management counseling and guidance, then management counseling and guidance, according to Joseph and Nurihsan (2004:25) is a variety of efforts to establish, maintain, and improve the quality of the program guidance and counseling through activities (1) the development of the program, (2) staff development, (3) utilization of resources, and (4) the development of structuring the policy. While the counseling and guidance service program itself was a planned activity was based on the measuring requirements (need to implement) that was manifested in the form of guidance and counseling program. Program counseling and

guidance in schools can be arranged in a macro for a three years, and micro for a period of one year as operating activities and facilitate special needs (Yusuf and Nurihsan, 2004:26-37).

Management of counseling and guidance as a process of planning, organizing, and controlling the implementation of counseling and guidance program, according to Yusuf and Nurihsan (2004:26-37), is carried out through:

1. Program development

The development of this programme should be aligned with the results of the study or analysis about the purpose and the objective condition of the school program, the achievement of the tasks of the development of the student, or the student's needs and problems, the objective conditions of the environment development the actual implementation of student, BK services in schools and community development (social and cultural world of the industry or company). Based on these considerations, then the program is should flexible, yet still idealistic. In developing these programs need to do the following things: (a) formulating the goals of service-oriented to the development of BK duties the development of students. (b) integrate the counseling and guidance program to the educational program at the school as a whole, both in the implementation of the program intrakulikuler extracurricular educational activities, as well as others. (c) organize the working mechanism of the organizational structure and personnel which allows the occurrence of coordination, communication and partnership between them, so that the program can be implemented of guidance and counseling services effectively and efficiently. (d) formulating the field content of the guidance, or guidance topics relevant to the development of the tasks of development of students. (e) formulate the type of tutoring service that support the launch of the program components of the service, good basic services program guidance, responsiveness, service or individual planning service. (f) recruitment of professional guidance officer (if possible), of which there are adequate by many students. (g) adequate means of supplementing such data collecting tools, tools, data storage and administration supplies adequate infrastructures, such as indoor guidance that includes supervising teachers work space, space of counseling and guidance groups, documentation, living room, library, and special fees for the purposes of correspondence,

home visit, upgrading, research, or other purposes that support the achievement of the goal of counseling and guidance. (h) evaluate the programs that have been implemented.

2. Staff development

In order for the supervisor or other school personnel capable of providing guidance in quality, then it needs to be given to those additions, expansions, or deepening of concepts or specific skills about the guidance, in accordance with the job description (performance) respectively. Staff development forms it can be implemented through seminars, workshops or upgrading. Through the activities of the development is expected to the school personnel have the competencies or capabilities in accordance with the description of the work (performance) respectively.

3. The utilization of community resources

This aspect deals with the efforts of schools to establish cooperation with the elements of society that is considered relevant to the improvement of the quality of counselling. This partnership with parties such as: Government agencies, private agencies, organizations of the profession (IPBI: Indonesia's guidance Officer Bonds) now ABKIN (Counseling and Guidance Association of Indonesia), experts in a particular field such as psychologists, psychiatrist, doctors, and parents of the students, MGBK (Discussion of teacher counseling and guidance). This cooperation especially with the industry or the company (in the framework of the implementation of the practically lesson), and also with the Depnaker (stock analysis in order to work or employment).

4. The development or determination of policy

The implementation of guidance and counseling services in schools need supported by principal policy clearly. The policy was launched it should be facilitated (gives ease and opportunities) for a smooth implementation of the program. The policies that need to be arranged concerning aspects: organizational structure, recruitment and staff development guidance, the provision of adequate infrastructure and facilities, allocating operating of counseling and guidance expenses, and scheduling a special time for the incoming class for teachers, as a vehicle for the implementation of the programme are classical, and establish cooperation with the parties concerned.

A program of counseling and guidance services is not likely going to take over, and is reached when does not have a system of management (management), in the sense of quality made in clear, systematic and purposeful. The following aspects of program management system counseling and guidance services (Yusuh and Nurihsan, 2004:37-42).

- a. Agreement management, deal management concerns the process of assuring and developing the commitment of all parties in the school environment that the guidance and counseling program as integral part of the overall school program.
- b. Stakeholder Involvement, the school committee as a representation of the public or stakeholders requires awareness and understanding of the existence and importance of the counseling and guidance services in schools.
- c. Management and use of data, data usage in counseling and guidance service will guarantee every student to benefit from the counseling and guidance services. Counselors must demonstrate that each activity was implemented as a part of the integrity of the program counseling and guidance careful analysis based upon to the needs, achievements, and other student related data.
- d. Plan activities, activity plan is a detailed description of the program that describes the structure of the content of the program, both activities at school and outside school, to facilitate students achieve development task or competence.
- e. Timing, planning this time based on the content of the program and the support of management which should be made by the counselors. For example, for example, 80% of the time used to serve students directly and 20% used for managerial support.
- f. Calendar of activities, the program BK school that has been poured into the activity plan needs to be scheduled into the shape of a calendar of activities. Annual calendar includes events calendar, semiannual, monthly, and weekly.
- g. Schedule of activities, guidance and counseling program can be implemented in the form of (a) direct contact, and (b) without direct contact with students. Regarding the schedule of activities of adult guidance, it's already got the legality of Government, that is, with the publication of Ministerial Regulation No. 22 from Diknas Year 2006. In the

structure of the curriculum set forth in the Candy, listed the material self development for 2 hours/week, which apply to all units of the elementary and secondary education.

- h. Budget activities, need to be designed with careful consideration of how the budget needed to support the implementation of the program. This budget should be entered into the budget and expenditures of the school.
- i. Preparation of the facility, the facility was expected to be available in the school, namely:
 - (1) the place of activities, which include working space Counsellor, space services for group guidance and counseling, guest lounge, library, and administration;
 - (2) instruments and the completeness of the administration, such as: question form students and parents, interviews, observation, guidance counseling, format the format of the units of the service, and referral letter format;
 - (3) books, guide books information about advanced studies or courses, modul of guidance and counseling, service annual program book, program semester, case book, diary, interviews, the activity report service, attendance data, and books the realization of the activities of counseling and guidance;
 - (4) electronic devices (such as computers, and tape recorder); and
 - (5) filing cabinets (storage of documents and data of students).
- j. Control program, control of management program services was coordinator of counselor, which sued to have the traits of a good leadership that can allow a good communication with all of the existing staff.

Although the counseling and guidance programme management has been clearly the procedure in accordance with national educational goals, but in some schools still found the existence of phenomena related to the organization of education, such as: (1) focus primary school a lot more on the development of academic competencies-cognitive. (2) Determining educational policy at the school level to understand the counseling and guidance with individual meetings (counseling) and especially function in addressing the issues of students (curative function). (3) counseling and guidance as part of the school has not been able to prove that a quality performance. A lack of quality counseling program that suits your needs, make students, school administrators, and stakeholders is difficult give confidence in

counseling and guidance. (4) the evaluation of the program counseling and guidance with the scientific method of the school has not been developed.

The Government created the role of school management standards that ensure the educational process in academic aspects (fields of study) and non-academic (counseling and guidance). This standard can maintain balance and discretion for guidance and counseling in the school to provide the services that best suit the needs of the students. This balance requires a standard process, for example, a rule that requires the presence of group guidance services/classical to reach all students, and all stakeholders. Guidance and counseling in school not too need a standard content because the content of guidance and counseling was based on student needs. Even if there is a curriculum of counseling and guidance formulated nationally, or provincial level, or a smaller area, it is not necessarily aligned with conditions and cultural background of a typical learner at school.

Based on the above description, it can be drawn in red thread, that a secondary school vocational counseling and guidance services through the developed, there are still many shortcomings that need to be dealt with, up to respond to various changes and demands of the world education. Therefore, in order to embody various things, the need for studies related to the management of the implementation of counseling and guidance in vocational secondary schools in order to get a clear description about the real of management pattern developed by Vocational secondary schools. Thus, the research conducted this dual function, the first from the point of view of the researcher, the research was conducted in order to obtain a picture or profile of counseling and guidance management of Vocational secondary school. Second, from the point of view of the school, this research can be viewed as an evaluation of the program management of counseling and guidance in the school. Thus the purpose of this research is to gain an overview of management counseling and guidance as well as the process of the implementation of counseling and guidance in vocational high school.

B. Methods

This form of research conducted the survey because of the kind of research including the study took a sample of a population and use observation and interview as a data collection tool staple (Singarimbun and Efendi, 2008:3). The study also considered a descriptive research with qualitative approach (Creswell. 1994:68). As for the object of research was implementation of guidance and counseling management program in vocational high school. Data source this study is a teacher at SMK Negeri BK I Badegan Ponorogo and coordinator of guidance and counseling. A method of data mining research is structured interview (interview with a guide).

Data analysis research was a qualitative analysis of the top notes interview and observational researchers. The results of the interview at SMK Negeri I Badegan, Ponorogo (in the form of a written report) presented by the teacher supervisor and coordinator of the BK. then the data is analyzed and then described by researchers.

This research was conducted at the vocational secondary school state of one in Badegan Country Ponorogo, East Java, a school which aims at delivering graduates to the level of the plenary as perfect person aligned with national Education Vision milestone achievement plenary in 2025. SMK Negeri I Badegan as the Organization of education, although he was only six years, i.e. Since the year 2005, but already growing rapidly with the number of students reaching about 1200 to total overall grade.

The object of the research was the focus in this research was the management counseling and guidance that was in the SMKN I Badegan. The counseling and guidance service at SMK Negeri I Badegan since the founding of the school in 2005 was carried out in a simple and tends to be unconditioned or just a complement of Legal Team in school (a unit of work that execute disciplinary actions for students) called "Tatib". Therefore, there was not much that can be excavated from the implementation of counseling and guidance at the time, due to its role in control and controlling students was more "Tatib" Team act as "police school". The existence of the guidance and counseling service at SMK Negeri I Badegan, could be felt for a year lately, which is new in 2010. This is because these schools get new one teacher of counseling and guidance, and until the time this research was

conducted, yet getting adding counselors with qualified teachers counseling and guidance. One person has been supervising teacher doing his role well, though the comparison the ratio is 1:1200, a figure that makes no sense, if one person should handle 1200 students, but in fact such, recently after the last one semester, the principal assigning one person teacher subjects to help the supervising teacher assignments. Overall the implementation of counseling and guidance at SMK Negeri I Badegan take place either, thanks to the work of a maximum of the BK personnel, which has a dual role as school counselor, also doubles task as coordinator of counseling and guidance service.

SMK Negeri I Badegan has three departments, namely the Department of TKR (Light Vehicle Engineering), TKJ (computer and network), as well as the grammar of Boga. Each Department has its own specifications. Department of TKR, has the purpose to master, develop and apply the science of automotive engineering with competencies that will be achieved by graduates as technicians or light vehicle mechanics, vehicle Assembly, machine operators and the design of the vehicle, as well as in the field of the engine and other automotive. Department of computer engineering and networks, preparing graduates who are faithful, noble character and have academic and professional ability in the field of computer programming. Competencies will be owned graduates are professionals in the field of network and system programmers, software, Assembly, computer software engineer, computer operators. Majoring of Boga, has the goal of producing graduates who have academic and professional qualifications with the mastery of the theory and techniques of cooking. The ultimate goal of preparing graduates to be professional as expert chef cooking various types of cuisine of Indonesia, Europe, Arabian, and various other world famous cuisine.

In support of the goals of the school are manifesting through the third department. The guidance and counselling service have been trying everything possible by using the "pattern of 17 Plus" to maximize the variety of facilities and infrastructure limited. Because in addition to the room of BK was not yet available, a variety of facilities and infrastructure associated with management counseling and guidance have also recently provided gradually by the supervising teacher.

The implementation of counseling and guidance at SMK Negeri I Badengan use "pattern 17 Plus" by maximizing various facilities and infrastructure are limited. Because in addition to the room of BK is not yet available, a variety of facilities and infrastructure associated with the management of the counseling and guidance also recently provided gradually by the supervising teacher. Like to says that the school counselor cleared forests to open up new land, due to the existence of the counseling and guidance were not have an infrastructure, even the orientation and work description have not known correctly by all elements of the school. So the task of supervising the teachers more weight, because of the socialization service has two objectives, namely students and other school elements.

C. discussions and Deliberations

Research results related to the management of the implementation of counseling and guidance program at SMK Negeri 1 Badegan, can generally be categorized into three sections, namely:

1. The counseling and guidance program planning in SMK N I Badegan. The data was successfully retrieved and analyzed related to program management planning of guidance and counselling at SMK Negeri I Badegan include:

a. Feasibility study related to social and environmental needs assessment of students. Based on the results of the data mining that SMK Negeri I Badegan did a feasibility study by digging the data students early in the school year with method (question form, interviews, process data/private student book). As for the process of the feasibility study conducted at SMK Negeri 1 Badegan in the holding the identification of priority activities and feasibility study of guidance and counseling programs, including some of the following stages: preparation phase, determination of criteria of success evaluation, determination of the instruments, the execution of the activities, results, analysis and interpretation of the stage or the interpretation and reporting of results.

b. Planning and consultation program of guidance and counseling. SMK Negeri Badegan has done programs planning first before being implemented. This planning related to drafting aitem-aitem or other types of support services and activities will be conducted in one school

year. In addition, the planning was also related to the provision of facilities and infrastructure. Moreover, in this land of SMK I Badegan still having service room yet, while still being the one with part of student room, so that in the planning of these facilities should always be included. After the order was made, the program plan report teacher mentors are usually double the plan report, then consultation its plan with the head of the school. If the plan is not aligned with the program activities of the school, and there was no budget for implementation of the specific plan, then the principal does not recommend to do.

Therefore, as a consequence of planning guidance and counseling program at SMK Negeri I Badegan it a lot based on the priority scale. This means that where a student needs urgent and which ones need to be looked at in the implementation of the program. Although the results of the feasibility study reflects the priority issues that the counseling and guidance was viewed essential based on the excavation of the needs of the students and describing the need in full (field of study, career, personal, and social). The following are descriptions of the results of the program planning of counseling and guidance at SMKN I Badegan, can be seen in table 1.

Table 1. Counseling and Guidance Implementation of Program Planning at SMK Negeri I Badegan

No	Kind Of Activity	Implementation Time	Result	Description
1	Feasibility study	25 April-15 May	implemented with good	follow-up program plan for one year ahead
2	Compose the BK program (annual, semiannual, and monthly)	20 May-01 June	Carried out properly, is composed of one BK program package for a year	Follow-up program plan consultation submission to the head of school
3	Consultation on proposed BK program	01 June-13 June	Carried out properly, and are approved to do	Follow-up on the development of the program
4	Provision of facilities means & infrastructure of BK	-	Yet	No budget funds, a place so one in the student management
5	The provision of budget implementation of BK	-	Yet	No budget funds

c. Socialization of counseling and guidance program in the neighborhood school and outside school. Counseling and guidance program socialization in this case is the delivery of information about the program and all things related to counseling and guidance in school to the relevant parties, such as students, teachers, principals, and parents, as well as the Foundation (for private schools). Socialization program is usually done after a proposal approved program plan and approved by the principal. Socializing done to; (1) the entire elements, such as school principals, teachers and staff employees in a meeting of the Board of teachers. (2) through the counseling and guidance services to all parties (students, teachers, parents), including through the “MOS” and the activities of the guidance of classical groups. (3) parents through teachers meetings with parents/caregivers. (4) to stakeholders outside of school through partnerships.

2. Implementation of counseling and guidance program management

The data was successfully retrieved and analyzed related to implementation of the management program at SMK Negeri BK I Badegan includes five aitem, among others:

a. Implementation of the group guidance or classical. Implementation groups guidance or classical in SMK Negeri I Badegan planned for was provided for all students in all grade levels (X, XI, XII) regular (scheduled), but because counseling and guidance personnel just one person who was also a coordinator, then implementation groups guidance or classical was only done in class XII. This is done with the consideration of the priority scale, grade XII will be deemed passed and immediately get a job or go on to College, more in need of various his insight, knowledge and skills that can be used as provision in the community.

As for the case of a distribution of data per class to the overall problem and violation can be seen that kind of total score problems or violations on most class XII Mercy to reach 978 points, then class X Yamaha 904, then class XII Renault to reach 885. Thus it can be concluded that students with a score of the most problematic are in class XII Mercy.

b. Execution of counseling services individually. SMK Negeri I Badegan provide Individual counseling services, with a medium frequency (range 1-3 students per day), there are also individual counseling service was scheduled by calling their learning achievements of students was low, do violations of the discipline and conduct of the school. Percentage of

number of students that chest counseling individually at SMK Negeri I Badegan can be seen in table 2.

Table 2. The distribution of Cases experienced by students at SMK Negeri I Badegan

No	Case Field	Students Case	Number	%	Action
1	Personal	Hair somewhat longish	18	4.13	Sanctions with cut
		Smoking	8	1.83	Rebuked, sanctions, guidance
		HP (with porn picture/content)	10	2.29	Confiscated, Sanctions, guidance
		Police arrested	1	0.22	Sanctions and case conference
		Courting	20	4.59	Sanction and guidance
		Pregnant	7	1.60	Issued
		Low self-esteem	10	2.29	Counseling
		Less Confident	16	3.67	Counseling
		Can't wake up early	17	3.90	Contacted and guidance
		Ease anxious	21	4.82	Counseling
2	Social	The social attribute of the uniform is not complete	40	9.19	Sanctions and guidance
		Wayward to teachers	11	2.52	Sanctions and guidance
		Play HP when lesson	15	3.44	Rebuked, sanctions, guidance
		Bring an camera HP	23	5.28	Disita, sangsi, bimbingan
		Difficult to communicate with others	26	5.97	Counseling
3	Learning	Arrive late often	43	9.88	Sanctions and guidance
		Alpha without permission	31	7.12	Sanctions and guidance
		Donnot do the task/homework	25	5.74	Sanctions and guidance
		Did not do the flag ceremony	29	6.66	Sanctions and guidance
		Strike to school	25	5.74	Home visit
		Difficult to concentrate	15	3.44	Counseling
4	Career	Career study confused	24	5.51	Guidance
Total			435	100 %	

As for the percentage of troubled students based on the results of searches on data breach, and reports that have been received, as well as the counseling and guidance percentage against the total number of students in SMK N I Badegan ever handled by counseling and guidance, then it can be seen in table 3 the following:

Table 3. Distribution Percentage of Problematic Students at SMK Negeri I Badegan

No	Category of Students Problem	Score of Violations	Amount	%	Description
1	Weight	71 – 80	10	1	This category of students problem in all of classes at SMKN I Badegan
2	Medium	51-70	20	2	
3	Mild	16 – 50	179	18	
4	Normal /no problem	0 – 15	771	79	
Total			980	100 %	

c. Counseling and guidance services for parents and families of students. Counseling and guidance services provided for parents and families of students (in this case the family including environmental) include home visits, visits the place of stay, meeting counseling and guidance personnel with parents/caregivers, seminars for parents, the giving of information to the parents/guardians of students progress report form. Counseling and guidance services for parents or family of origin students in SMK Negeri I Badegan only done for severe cases. Almost no service was a counseling and guidance planned provided for parents/families that are developmental, prevention, and maintenance.

d. Implementation of counseling and guidance in General. The process of the implementation of counseling and guidance in SMKN I Badegan go well, this can be seen from the enthusiasm of the students against the existence of counseling and guidance in schools, which previously still use pattern that has not been a clear and well-organized. For more details the data that was successfully identified, can be seen in table 4.

Table 4. The distribution of the BK Program at SMK Negeri I Badegan

No	Type of Activity	Time Activity	Amount
1	Orientation	The first week of Desember	2
2	Information	1,2th week of July, Aug, Nov	7
3	Placement & channeling	Incidental	5
4	Content mastery	July-November	25

5	Individual counseling	August-December	17
6	Group counseling	August, September, November	4
7	Group guidance	September, October, November	5
8	Consultation	August, September, December	4
9	Mediation	-	-
10	Instrument Applications	September	1
11	Data collecting	November	1
12	Case conference	October, November	2
13	Home visit	July-December	12
14	Display libraries	-	-
15	Case hand over	-	-

e. Evaluation and supervision program of counseling and guidance. The counseling and guidance program evaluation conducted by SMK Negeri I Badegan the form of gathering opinions and/or impression of the teachers and staff of counseling and guidance with the method of scientific research using instrument data digger written and interview for the now dig the feedback on the program BK from students. This type of question form or questionnaire that was used a question form for teachers and all other school elements, and then question form for students, and now to his own counseling and guidance personnel. The contents of the questionnaire were aitem material associated with programs that have been conducted, as well as related services that counseling and guidance has done.

Implementation of the supervision carried out by the trustees of the educational units counseling and guidance district level took place in April every years. The result was excellent from all surveillance materials that become aitem, everything can be accepted by a team of trustees, so that it can be categorized program implementation guidance and counselling at SMK Negeri I badegan been up to expectations.

3. Organization and personnel of counseling and guidance in SMK I Badegan

The data was successfully retrieved and analyzed related to organizational and human resources personnel BK in SMK Negeri I Badegan include three items, among others:

a. Organizations and characteristics of BK personnel. In Indonesia own ratio of students was (1:150), in the school was a very unnatural ratio. It was because personnel BK just one teacher the remaining Coordinator of BK. As for organizational structures developed in SMK

Negeri I Badegan, among others have coordinator positions with BK under the head of the school. In terms of educational background, the personnel background Undergraduate Psychology Education.

b. The views and support of elements of the role and function of school counselling and guidance. Basically not all elements of the school to understand the pattern of employment guidance and counselling which uses a new paradigm with a pattern of BK 17 Plus, most still assume BK as policeman the school, though it's been completely different. Therefore, support for the BK is still less satisfying.

c. Cooperation relationships and partnerships built personnel counselling and guidance. Data successfully identified related to the partnership, is the following: (1) the partnership school in BK with other parties in the curative function, namely partnership with police in the handling of the case of rasia drugs, and a partnership with the medical team for a pregnancy test. (2) partnerships with other parties in the BK run preventive, developmental, function maintenance. Partnership with the police in the giving of information about drugs, crime, and law. (3) partnerships with other related parties BK career development and advanced studies. In collaboration with the college students who wish to enter a destination. While career collaborating with various providers of jobs from various agencies who meet the qualifications for courses that are in the SMKN I Badegan.

Based on the results of the research that has been conducted related management program implementation guidance and counselling at SMK Negeri 1 Badegan, can be explained that if referred to in guidance and counselling management said was Joseph and Nurihsan (2004:25) counseling and guidance is that the management of various efforts to establish, maintain, and improve the quality of guidance and counseling programs through activities (1) the development of the program, (2) staff development, (3) utilization of resources, and (4) the development of structuring the policy.

Based on the four elements of management that can be explained that the guidance and counseling of SMKN I Badegan had been trying to do and develop it. First, in terms of program development. The procedure has been done already belongs to a professional and appropriate standards, since through the mechanism of a careful planning process feasibility

study, consulting programs, and the process of socialization of the program on the environment inside and outside of the school. Second, in terms of staff development. The effort that has been done already, it's just that the proposed addition of counseling and guidance teacher against education service has not been realized, so the condition that occurs is the inequality ratio of number of students with a number of teachers that there was no comparable with 1:1200 students. Although the school had one teacher subjects to help but it is still far from standards, where should the composition of the ideal teacher or school counselor comparison was 1:150 students. Third, in terms of the utilization of the existing resources, the school has been doing various businesses by making use of some teachers of subjects to help the implementation of guidance and counseling, but not a maximum, since many have yet to understand the counseling and guidance work program. As well as the facilities and infrastructure are not yet available, appropriate service standards BK BK room. even still become one with the student, so that this hampers the implementation of counseling and guidance service. Fourth, in terms of Setup development policy. Policies issued by the school has not met the expectations of guidance and counseling. Because of the variety of aspects still haven't gotten the maximum support. Starting from procurement of staff, provision of facilities, counseling and guidance system support, to fund the implementation of the programme budget could not support the activities of the counseling and guidance at SMK Negeri I Badegan.

As for the counseling and guidance programs that have been developed in SMK N I Badegan, in general already refers to a comprehensive programme of guidance and counseling, because the program already developed systemic in nature and in accordance with some of the following elements (Erford, 2004):

1. Who can formulate needs Assessment of students and other important stakeholders such as parents, community of peers, teachers, school administrators, and others. Teacher of counseling and guidance parties has implemented the assessment through a feasibility study the scientific with the identification of the needs and problems of the students at the time of the design of the program was done.

2. Counseling and guidance service outreach to students and other relevant stakeholders such as parents, the community of origin of the students, the community of peers, teachers, schools and communities in General. On this very aitem f because practically the program is indeed intended for all elements of the school including the family, but also due to the limited personnel of counseling and guidance owned by SMK N I Badegan hasn't been able to implement to the maximum.

3. The Program of counseling and guidance systemic can involve stakeholders as the recipient of the service, and as partners in giving the relevant service. For example, in order to create a healthy family environment and is conducive to the growing swell of students, the school can organize educational activities of students parents. On this third grains, new activities can be run only on the family home visits troubled students. Whereas the development of intensive cooperation relationships regularly with the stake holders and guardians of students only as at the confluence of the guardian when the new school year alone, moreover no program associated opimalisasi sustainable self development students through a partnership with parents or guardians.

4. Evaluation of process, outcome, and impact that reach out to students and stake holder. The systemic program of counseling and guidance carried out with a long-term goal of forming a possible development environment (Erford, 2004). Evaluation of the process, outcomes and impact of the guidance and counselling have been conducted by the counseling and guidance was concerned. This evaluation was done at the end of the year survey procedures for lessons, then the result is reported to the principal.

D. Closing

Based on the results of research related to the management of the implementation of guidance and counseling, then it can be inferred that the SMK Negeri I Badegan had done a comprehensive work programme of counseling and guidance, although support personnel and facilities as well as infrastructure is still minimal. . Therefore, the various obstacles that exist are in fact not an obstacle to the correct doctrine counseling and guidance personnel towards the vision and mission of the counseling and guidance. Finally, the most appropriate

suggestions addressed to the leadership of SMK Negeri I Badegan as well as other school elements to provide full support to the existence and success of the entire program at SMK Negeri I Badegan.

On the other hand, not only the ability of the production management course which must be owned by the school counselor psychic abilities but also understanding learners. As said by A. Said Hasan Basri (2012) that the school counselor or teacher supervisor to equip themselves with the modality of knowledge, competence and skills are adequate. One of these modalities, namely knowledge about human psychic activities, which will be parsed further in an effort to give a broader picture that knowledge about human psychic activity is very important and useful in the implementation of the Ministry of guidance and counselling in schools. Because according to A. Said Hasan Basri (2012) that guidance and counselling puts psychology science as the Foundation and became a modalities in an effort to understand the dynamics of human psychological specifically related to the activity of the psychic. This needs to be elaborated further, because of the views about human psychology which also targeted guidance and counseling many contributing to the guidance itself. Psychology looked at the man as a creature who has the soul certainly can give you an idea of the human soul that reflects a wide range of behavior and activity in daily life.

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